

COMMISSION D'ACCÈS À L'INFORMATION DU QUÉBEC
Oversight Division

Complaint

Pursuant to s. 123 Act respecting Access to documents held by public bodies and the Protection of personal information

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PART I – OVERVIEW

1. The Ministère de l'Éducation du Québec (MEQ) currently uses an artificial intelligence system to flag elementary school children at risk of dropping out before graduating high school¹. We submit that the system breaches the *Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels*² (*Loi sur l'accès*) and it should not be used until the MEQ remedies these violations.
2. The algorithm pulls together 1,500 data points to generate its predictions. The dataset on which it relies contains sensitive information such as the immigration status of the students or their medical history³. The system does not satisfy any of the four steps of the necessity test required for lawfulness under s. 64 of *Loi sur l'accès*.
 - a. The AI system does not pursue a legitimate objective because its purpose is ill-defined and overbroad.
 - b. The AI system is not rationally connected to the objective of “using data to inform educational and organizational decisions” because the algorithm’s predictions are biased and lack accuracy.
 - c. The AI system does not minimally impair the right to privacy because (1) it processes more data than necessary and (2) it does not comply with the *Val-des-Cerfs* guidelines on how to protect students’ privacy when deploying an algorithm to predict dropout.
 - d. The benefits of the AI system are limited and they do not outweigh its negative impacts on the right to privacy.
3. These violations can be attributed to the MEQ’s failure to conduct a privacy impact assessment (PIA). In *Val-des-Cerfs*, the Commission d'accès à l'information (CAI) assessed an earlier version of the AI system and found that it contravened *Loi sur l'accès*. It recommended conducting a PIA before deploying the AI system at scale. The MEQ ignored the recommendation.
4. The present case provides an opportunity for the CAI to establish clear precedents regarding the responsible use of AI by public organizations. When it issued the *Val-des-Cerfs* ruling, the *Loi modernisant des dispositions législatives en matière de protection des renseignements personnels* (*Bill 25*) had not yet fully entered into force. This case is an occasion for the CAI to revisit its ruling and make use of its new strengthened legal framework and powers.

¹ Z. Goudreault, “L’IA est mise au service de la lutte au décrochage scolaire. Mais à quel prix?” *Le Devoir* (14 Janvier 2026) (**Exhibit P-1**)

² *Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels*, CQLR c. A-2.1.

³ Québec, Éducation Québec, *Demande d'accès à des documents administratifs, dossier : 16310/24-757* (accessed 29 avril 2026) at pp. 4-5. (**Exhibit P-2**)

PART II - FACTS

5. This complaint marks the latest development in a matter that began in 2019. At the time, the Commission d'accès à l'Information (CAI) launched an investigation into an experimental project led by a school board and an accounting firm to determine if artificial intelligence could be used to help prevent student dropouts⁴.
6. In November 2022, the CAI released the findings of that investigation in the *Val-des-Cerfs* decision. It concluded that the experimental project contravened the *Loi sur l'accès*⁵. As *Bill 25* which granted the CAI broader powers to impose sanctions was not yet fully in force, the decision is mostly non-binding.
7. In parallel to the CAI's investigation, the MEQ started developing its own version of the drop out prediction algorithm initially designed by the Centre de services scolaires *Val-des-Cerfs*⁶. This new version of the algorithm is inconsistent with the *Val-des-Cerfs* recommendations. The plaintiff's case provides the CAI with an opportunity to enforce its 2022 findings.
8. The plaintiff is the mother of a child who attends an elementary school affiliated with the Centre de services scolaires des Premières-Seigneuries (hereafter, the School Board). She is concerned about the government's handling of her child's personal information, in particular, the School Board's use of artificial intelligence to process the personal information it holds about its students.
9. On December 10, 2024, she received an email informing her that the School Board had started using artificial intelligence to process the personal information it holds about its students. The goal of this new data processing was to generate risk indicators to prevent dropouts. The email sent by the school board's Directrice Générale reads as follows:

[...]

Dans le cadre de nos activités pour améliorer la réussite éducative de nos élèves, nous avons recours à certains outils numériques utilisant l'intelligence artificielle. Ils permettent de générer des indicateurs visant notamment à réduire les risques de décrochage scolaire.

⁴ *Centre de services scolaire du-Val-des-Cerfs (anciennement Commission scolaire du Val-des-Cerfs) CAI 1020040-S* at par. 2-3.

⁵ *Val-des-Cerfs*, par. 53-54.

⁶ P. Faucher, "Un outil anti-décrochage sera utilisé dans toutes les écoles du Québec", *La Tribune*, (30 janvier 2025). (**Exhibit P-3**) "Tous les centres de services scolaires du Québec utiliseront bientôt un outil d'intelligence artificielle visant à prévenir le décrochage scolaire et inspiré de celui conçu à Val-des-Cerfs, à Granby. [...] l'outil retenu par Québec s'inspire de celui de Val-des-Cerfs, mais en utilisant un modèle mathématique et une interface différente. Il fonctionne toutefois sur les mêmes principes"

Des renseignements personnels sont recueillis lors de l'inscription et lors du cheminement scolaire de votre enfant. Ils pourraient être utilisés par ces outils et permettre, par des comparaisons ou des croisements de données, de créer de nouveaux renseignements personnels (ex. : création d'un indicateur portant sur le risque de décrochage scolaire de votre enfant).

Veillez noter que :

- des mesures de confidentialité et de sécurité sont mises en place conformément aux meilleures pratiques ;
- les renseignements personnels ne serviront qu'à des fins éducatives et d'accompagnement des élèves ;
- l'accès est strictement limité aux personnes dont les renseignements personnels sont nécessaires dans le cadre de leurs fonctions.

Pour toute question en lien avec le présent sujet, nous vous invitons à communiquer avec le secrétariat général, par courriel à l'adresse secgen@cssps.gouv.qc.ca.

Veillez recevoir nos meilleures salutations.

[...]⁷

10. On December 11, 2024, the plaintiff asked the Secrétariat Général of the School Board not to use her child's personal information to produce AI-generated indicators for dropout prevention purposes. On January 18, 2025, she sent a follow-up email, reiterating her desire to have her child's data withdrawn from the system.

11. On January 28th, the School Board responded:

[...]

La solution d'intelligence artificielle pour soutenir la prévention du décrochage scolaire est une initiative du ministère de l'Éducation. Elle permet d'analyser et d'agir rapidement auprès d'élèves qui présentent des facteurs de risque

La collecte et l'utilisation de ces renseignements ont un caractère obligatoire afin de permettre au Centre de services scolaire des Premières-Seigneuries (CSSPS) d'être opérationnel, de s'acquitter de sa mission et de ses fonctions et de se conformer à la *Loi sur le ministère de l'Éducation, du Loisir et du Sport*.

Conformément à l'article 67 de la *Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels*, un organisme public peut, sans le

⁷ Exhibit P-4

consentement de la personne concernée, communiquer un renseignement personnel à toute personne ou tout organisme, si cette communication est nécessaire à l'application d'une loi au Québec.

[...]⁸

12. Three important elements are worth highlighting in this correspondence: first, the AI system is an initiative from the MEQ, not the School Board. Second, the MEQ considers that its data processing is mandatory. Third, it considers that a parent's objection does not constitute an obstacle to its processing of personal information.
13. The plaintiff received confirmation of these elements during a meeting with Ms. Charlène Marois, a régisseuse at the Centre de services scolaire des Premières-Seigneuries, On February 12, 2025. Ms. Marois told the plaintiff that school boards do not have the power to remove data from the system. The AI system is the MEQ's project, and the school board does not have "marge de manoeuvre" regarding its implementation.
14. In light of this information, the Plaintiff filed a complaint before the MEQ in which she requested, once again, the withdrawal of her child's personal information from the AI system.
15. On February 17, 2025, the MEQ's commissaire aux plaintes, Mr. Maxime Miville-Chartré, refused to grant the plaintiff's request. He contends that allowing people to opt out from the AI system is impossible because it would impede the performance of the AI system. He also erroneously suggests that all confidentiality matters have been addressed by the CAI in the de *Val-des-Cerfs* ruling. The full email reads as follows:

[...]

Nous avons bien reçu vos préoccupations concernant le projet-pilote de déploiement progressif d'outils utilisant l'intelligence artificielle.

Tout d'abord, il s'agit bien d'un projet qui est mis de l'avant par le ministère de l'Éducation. Les CSS doivent mettre ne place [sic] le projet et ils ont l'obligation d'informer les parents de ce dernier. Cependant, aucune autorisation supplémentaire n'est requise. Les parents ne peuvent pas exiger que les renseignements personnels concernant leur enfant ne soient pas utilisés dans un tel outil. Le retrait des renseignements personnels concernant un élève risquerait :

- D'affecter la qualité des résultats du modèle d'intelligence artificielle en réduisant la taille de l'échantillon;
- D'entraîner des biais dans les résultats;
- De compromettre la performance globale du modèle.

⁸ Exhibit P-4

Pour votre information, toutes les questions de confidentialités [sic] des renseignements personnels sur ce projet du MEQ ont été soumis [sic] à La commission d'accès à l'information du Québec (CAI) et ce dernier a rendu sa décision. Les jugements de la CAI sont publics et vous pouvez le consulter au lien suivant : <https://decisions.cai.gouv.qc.ca/cai/ss/fr/item/520925/index.do>. Le jugement est pour un CSS en particulier, mais sa conclusion s'applique à l'ensemble des CSS.

Le jugement explique assurément mieux que moi les arguments qui appuient sa décision. Je fais tout de même parvenir les commentaires des parents à mes autorités pour qu'ils en prennent connaissance.

[...] ⁹

16. Following this email, the plaintiff wrote separately to the MEQ and the Ministère de la cybersécurité et du numérique to obtain a copy of the Privacy Impact Assessment conducted before deploying the dropout prediction algorithm.
17. On March 4, the directeur de l'encadrement et de l'utilisation éthique de l'intelligence artificielle, Mr. Martin Soucy, responded that the Ministère de la cybersécurité et du numérique had not been involved in assessing the MEQ's AI system as it is the data holder's purview:

[...]

En réponse à votre demande, nous désirons vous informer que le MCN n'a pas été impliqué dans l'évaluation du projet cité dans votre courriel.

À titre informatif, nous tenons à vous souligner que l'obligation de réaliser une évaluation des facteurs relatifs à la vie privée (EFVP) prévue à la Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels (RLQR, chapitre A-2.1), notamment dans le cas d'un [projet d'acquisition, de développement et de refonte d'un système d'information ou de prestation électronique de services](#) qui implique des renseignements personnels, est entrée en vigueur le 22 septembre 2023.

La réalisation de cette EFVP relève de l'organisme public qui détient les renseignements personnels concernés par le projet. En effet, chaque organisme public est responsable de protéger les renseignements personnels qu'il recueille, détient, utilise, communique et conserve. Il en est ainsi imputable. Il doit s'assurer de mettre en place des structures et des règles et adopter des pratiques pour les

⁹ Exhibit P-4

protéger de manière adéquate. [...] ¹⁰

18. For his part, Mr. Miville-Chartré from the MEQ replied that the only document he had concerning the AI system's privacy implications was the *Val-des-Cerfs* ruling.

[...]

Je n'ai que le jugement de la CAI que je vous ai déjà fait parvenir. <https://decisions.cai.gouv.qc.ca/cai/ss/fr/item/520925/index.do> Il est possible de faire une demande d'accès au MEQ pour obtenir l'information si c'est une information que nous détenons. (underlining added) [...] ¹¹

19. On March 3, 2025, on Mr. Miville-Chartré's suggestion, the plaintiff filed an access-to-information request before the MEQ. On March 22, the MEQ informed the plaintiff that it could not locate the document within the statutory 30-day period to respond to an access to information request. On April 15, the MEQ'S Responsable de l'accès aux documents, Ms. Ingrid Barakatt, confirmed that no PIA had been completed yet:

[...]

En effet, à la date de votre demande, le Ministère ne détient pas de document pouvant y répondre. Le processus d'évaluation des facteurs relatifs à la vie privée suit présentement son cours pour ce programme. [...] ¹²

20. On April 4, 2025, the Plaintiff filed a complaint with the Protecteur du citoyen¹³. The complaint raised three issues: First, the MEQ did not conduct a privacy impact assessment which contravened the *Val-des-Cerfs* ruling and the *Loi sur l'Accès*. Second, the MEQ did not comply with the requirements of a recent administrative directive adopted to ensure the responsible deployment of AI in the public sector¹⁴. Finally, there is currently no well-defined process through which individuals impacted by the government's use of AI can seek redress.

21. On May 26, 2025, the Protecteur du citoyen informed the plaintiff that it did not have jurisdiction over her complaint¹⁵, and transferred the file to the Commission d'accès à

¹⁰ **Exhibit P-4**

¹¹ **Exhibit P-4**

¹² **Exhibit P-6**

¹³ **Exhibit P-5**

¹⁴ *Énoncé de principe pour une utilisation responsable de l'intelligence artificielle par les organismes public* AM 2024-02 (QC)

¹⁵ **Exhibit P-7** "Or, c'est la Commission de l'accès à l'information (Commission) qui a compétence pour examiner votre plainte en cette matière"

l'information¹⁶. On June 4, 2025, the CAI acknowledged receipt of the file. However, no investigation was opened.

PART III - ANALYSIS

22. The plaintiff tried to object to the school board's use of artificial intelligence to process her son's personal information and encountered several administrative obstacles. Throughout the process, it became clear that neither the school board, the MEQ, nor the Ministère de la cybersécurité et du numérique had a complete view of the project. The lack of an accountable leader led to the design of an AI system that is inconsistent with Quebec's regulatory framework for digital technologies¹⁷.
23. Our initial complaint raised arguments that fell within the Protecteur du citoyen's jurisdiction rather than the CAI's, which may explain the CAI's decision not to open an investigation. In light of the new arguments set out below, which fall squarely within the CAI's jurisdiction, we ask that the CAI open an investigation under section 123 of the *Loi sur l'accès*. Otherwise, the plaintiff will be left without recourse to challenge the processing of her son's personal information.

A. THE AI SYSTEM FAILS THE NECESSITY TEST ON EVIDENTIARY GROUNDS

24. The MEQ relies on the exception set out in s. 64. al. 2 of *Loi sur l'accès* to collect personal information about students without parental consent¹⁸. This exception benefits only organizations whose data collection activities are deemed 'necessary' for the accomplishment of their mission. To establish 'necessity' under s. 64, the MEQ must demonstrate that its data collection satisfies the criteria of the test articulated in *Société de transport de la Ville de Laval c. X*.

¹⁶ **Exhibit P-8**, "En application de l'article 173 de la Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels, nous vous informons de la plainte reçue par le Protecteur du citoyen sur une matière de la compétence de la Commission d'accès à l'information. Vous trouverez-ci-joint la plainte écrite reçue au Protecteur du citoyen portant sur l'utilisation des renseignements personnels des élèves dans le cadre d'un projet utilisant l'intelligence artificielle en soutien à la prévention du décrochage scolaire."

¹⁷ Art. 64, 65, 67 and 73, *Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels* CQLR c. A-2.1; Principe 1 (Respect des personnes et de la règle de droit), Principe 7 (Transparence), and Principe 9 (Principe de la responsabilité) *Énoncé de principe pour une utilisation responsable de l'intelligence artificielle par les organismes public* AM 2024-02 (QC)

¹⁸ Under *Val-des-Cerfs* the generation of drop out indicators is deemed a new collection. Since the MEQ generates the drop out indicators by relying on the school boards data, s. 64 al. 2 provides that the collection must be necessary to their common mission. Moreover, s. 67 of *Loi sur l'Accès* provides that the communication of personal information from the School Board to the MEQ has to be necessary for the application of an Act in Quebec. The School Board claims that this communication of personal information is necessary for the application of *Loi sur le ministère de l'Éducation, du Loisir et du Sport*. (Email from the School Board's secrétariat Général, January 25 2026)

Un renseignement sera donc nécessaire non pas lorsqu'il pourra être jugé absolument indispensable, ou au contraire simplement utile. Il sera nécessaire lorsque chaque fin spécifique poursuivie par l'organisme, pour la réalisation d'un objectif lié à ses attributions, sera légitime, importante, urgente et réelle, et lorsque l'atteinte au droit à la vie privée que pourra constituer la cueillette, la communication ou la conservation de chaque élément de renseignement sera proportionnelle à cette fin¹⁹.

25. The necessity test derives from the Oakes test, used to justify an infringement on a Charter Right. To be considered necessary, (1) the data generated by the algorithm must pursue a legitimate objective, (2) this objective must be rationally connected to the measure taken to achieve it—*i.e.* using AI to generate drop out risk indicators (3) the algorithm must be designed to impair as little as possible on students' right to privacy and data protection and (4) the benefits of the AI system must outweigh its negative impacts.
26. We submit that the MEQ's algorithm fails at every step of the test. This is due to the MEQ's decision not to conduct a privacy impact assessment. Conducting a privacy impact assessment would have allowed the MEQ to carefully design its algorithm to meet the necessity criterion.

1. The MEQ does not meet its Burden of Proof because it didn't Conduct a Privacy Impact Assessment

27. The MEQ bears the burden of proving that its AI system satisfies the 'necessity' test under the *Loi sur l'accès*. It cannot meet its burden of proof because it did not conduct a privacy impact assessment before deploying its algorithm. The main purpose of the PIA is to help organizations assess—and then demonstrate—that their data processing activities meet the proportionality and necessity criteria²⁰. By choosing not to conduct one, the MEQ failed to discharge its burden of proof.
28. A PIA is a mechanism aimed at preventing rule violations before they occur. Organizations have to demonstrate their compliance with *Loi sur l'accès* through a PIA before engaging in their data processing activities. This both incentivizes compliance and facilitates enforcement. Once they have gone through the process of explaining how they plan to comply with the *Loi sur l'accès*, organizations are unlikely to breach it. If they do, however, the PIA constitutes an evidentiary record that facilitates the investigation.

¹⁹ *Laval (Ville) c. X.*, 2003 CanLII 44085 (QC CQ), at par. 44.

²⁰ Commission d'accès à l'information, "Réaliser une Évaluation des Facteurs Relatifs à la vie privée - Guide d'accompagnement à la démarche et à sa documentation" (modified : avril 2024) at p. 5 "Par essence, l'EFVP constitue donc un outil précieux pour réfléchir à la nécessité et à la proportionnalité de votre projet et les démontrer, en tenant compte de ses objectifs et des risques d'atteinte à la vie privée qu'il engendre."

29. Naturally, as *ex ante* mechanisms, PIAs must be conducted before personal information starts being processed. Section 64 of *Loi sur l'accès* leaves no room for interpretation in this regard:

64. Nul ne peut, au nom d'un organisme public, recueillir un renseignement personnel si cela n'est pas nécessaire à l'exercice des attributions de cet organisme ou à la mise en oeuvre d'un programme dont il a la gestion.

Un organisme public peut toutefois recueillir un renseignement personnel si cela est nécessaire à l'exercice des attributions ou à la mise en oeuvre d'un programme de l'organisme public avec lequel il collabore pour la prestation de services ou pour la réalisation d'une mission commune.

La collecte visée au deuxième alinéa doit être précédée d'une évaluation des facteurs relatifs à la vie privée et s'effectue dans le cadre d'une entente écrite transmise à la Commission. L'entente entre en vigueur 30 jours après sa réception par la Commission.

30. The MEQ should have known that conducting a PIA was a mandatory step for deploying the AI system as the CAI had expressly recommended it in *Val-des-Cerfs*.

[61] RECOMMANDE à l'organisme de procéder à une évaluation des facteurs relatifs à la vie privée avant de procéder à ce déploiement et de la réviser de façon périodique²¹.

31. Yet on April 15, about eight months after it started rolling out its algorithm, the MEQ still hadn't conducted a privacy impact assessment:

En effet, à la date de votre demande, le Ministère ne détient pas de document pouvant y répondre. Le processus d'évaluation des facteurs relatifs à la vie privée suit présentement son cours pour ce programme²².

32. This admission proves that the algorithm was deployed in contravention of s. 64 of *Loi sur l'accès* and that the MEQ cannot provide the required evidence to meet the necessity test. Conducting a PIA is a long and demanding process, but it can ultimately make the difference between an ill-conceived technology and a truly rights-respecting system. An AI system designed without a PIA will also suffer further flaws.

B. THE AI SYSTEM FAILS THE NECESSITY TEST ON SUBSTANTIVE GROUNDS

1. The AI System does not Pursue a Legitimate Objective

33. The MEQ is deploying an AI system without having clearly defined its purposes. For this

²¹ *Val-des-Cerfs*, par. 61.

²² Exhibit P-6

reason, its data processing fails on the first step of the necessity test and must be held unlawful.

34. In December 2024, the school board informed parents that the objective of the MEQ’s AI system is to “générer des indicateurs visant notamment à réduire les risques de décrochage scolaire.” This objective is too broad to allow for a rigorous analysis.
35. In *RJR-MacDonald Inc. v. Canada (Attorney General)*, Justice La Forest highlighted the risks of working with overly broad objectives: “if the objective is stated too broadly, its importance may be exaggerated and the analysis compromised.”²³ In the landmark ruling *Carter v. Canada*, the Supreme Court rejected “the preservation of life” as an objective for the prohibition of medically assisted dying for this particular reason. Preserving life is a social value, not a policy objective²⁴. It is so broad that it could be used to justify virtually any Charter rights violation. Instead, the Supreme court selected the following objective: “preventing vulnerable persons from being induced to commit suicide at a time of weakness”.
36. Just like the objective in *Carter*, the objective proposed by the MEQ—i.e., reducing the risk of students dropping out of school—is the statement of a social value. It must be rejected because it encompasses too many different types of uses. Indeed, while using the results of the algorithm in an exploratory fashion to better understand factors leading to drop out could be a legitimate objective, the use of the predictions for resource allocation purposes, that is to say to determine which schools should receive additional funding, and which schools should face budget cuts, is not²⁵. Without clearly defined uses for the drop out risk indicators, the MEQ’s objective cannot be characterized as legitimate.

2. The AI System’s Benefits are not Proportionate to its Privacy Implications

37. Failure to pass the first step of the necessity analysis is sufficient to conclude that the collection of personal information is unnecessary and therefore unlawful. Although the analysis could stop here, we will proceed to the second part of the test to highlight further issues with the MEQ’s AI system and how it was deployed.
38. The second prong of the necessity test is divided into three sub-steps: first, the AI system

²³ *RJR-MacDonald Inc. v. Canada (Attorney General)*, 1995 CanLII 64 (SCC) at para 144.

²⁴ *Carter c. Canada (Procureur général)*, 2015 CSC 5 at para 76.

²⁵ Linking performance metrics to funding could encourage schools to manipulate their data in order to increase their funding : “Les systèmes d’IA peuvent encourager l’adoption de comportements dysfonctionnels, tels que l’exclusion d’élèves à risque élevé de décrochage par un établissement scolaire pour préserver son statut (OCDE, 2022), ou la modification de données pour augmenter le nombre d’élèves à risque dans un établissement scolaire en vue d’obtenir plus de financement.” See : Ministère de l’Éducation du Québec, “Recommandations éthiques de l’intelligence artificielle en éducation” (2026) at p. 20.

must be rationally connected to the objective it aims to achieve. Second, the AI system must be carefully designed to infringe as little as possible on the right to privacy. Third, the privacy implications of the AI system should not outweigh its benefits. The MEQ's AI system fails on all three fronts.

a) The AI System is not Rationally Connected to the Objective it Aims to Achieve

39. For the remainder of the necessity test, we will replace the MEQ's stated objective with a narrower one proposed by CTREQ, which is the organisation responsible for implementing the AI system in Quebec's schools. According to CTREQ, the algorithm aims to "éclairer les décisions pédagogiques et organisationnelles grâce aux données"²⁶.
40. The rationale underlying this objective is that evidence-based decision-making is desirable, and that algorithms can provide more precise data to support it. This rationale is flawed, as AI systems used for dropout prediction are prone to bias and are therefore ill-suited to provide reliable insights for decision-making. Simon Collin who holds the Canada Research Chair in Digital Equity in Education at UQAM, highlights the risk that drop out prediction systems produce more false positives for students from low-income or multi-ethnic families²⁷. In other words, students from these groups would be more likely to be identified as potential dropouts, even though they are, in fact, on track to succeed.
41. Relying on biased dropout prediction scores to make pedagogical and organizational decisions risks perpetuating inequalities. For instance, the algorithm's biased predictions could lead to students from low-income or multi-ethnic families being pushed towards less demanding programs in order to maximize their chances of graduating²⁸ or being expelled by schools seeking to improve their graduation rate²⁹.
42. This would constitute discrimination—that is, a distinction, based on protected grounds, that either imposes burdens, obligations, or disadvantages on an individual or group but not onto others or limits access to opportunities, benefits, and advantages available to other individuals

²⁶ Centre de transfert pour la réussite éducative du Québec, "Prévenir le décrochage par l'intelligence artificielle" (Accessed : 13 January, 2026) <https://www.ctreq.qc.ca/projets/prevenir-le-decrochage-par-lia-meq/>

²⁷ S. Collin et al "Enjeux éthiques et critiques de l'intelligence artificielle en éducation : une revue systématique de la littérature" (2023) 49-4 *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology* 1 at p. 8, 14, 16.

²⁸ At Georgia State University, a predictive algorithm used to improve graduation rates directed students of color to fields with less earning potential. **See** : L. Weinberg, *Smart University - Student Surveillance in the Digital Age*, (John Hopkins University Press, 2024) at p. 72.

²⁹ "Les systèmes d'IA peuvent encourager l'adoption de comportements dysfonctionnels, tels que l'exclusion d'élèves à risque élevé de décrochage par un établissement scolaire pour préserver son statut (OCDE, 2022)" **See** : Ministère de l'Éducation du Québec, "Recommandations éthiques de l'intelligence artificielle en éducation" (2026) at p. 20.

or groups in society³⁰. An AI system that steers decision-makers toward discriminatory outcomes cannot be said to improve decision-making. If the goal is to make better informed decisions—or *prendre des décisions plus éclairées*—decision-makers cannot rely on biased results. Therefore, the MEQ’s AI system cannot be found to be rationally connected to the objective of promoting better-informed decision-making.

b) The AI system does not Minimally Impair Pupils’ Right to Privacy

43. The next step of the proportionality analysis requires us to determine if the AI system is designed to have the smallest possible impact on the right to privacy and data protection. The answer to that question is negative too. The system fails on this second step for two reasons: first, the system processes more personal information than is necessary to achieve its objective. Second, the MEQ did not implement the recommendations made by the CAI in *Val-des-Cerfs* to ensure that the students’ data protection rights guaranteed by *Loi sur l’accès* were respected.

i. The AI System Runs Contrary to the Principle of Data Minimization

44. Data minimization is a key principle underlying *Loi sur l’accès*. This principle commands that the government adopts a minimalist approach in its data processing—only when a piece of personal information is needed to achieve a specific purpose can it be collected or used. While it has been challenged by the maximalist logic of big data and artificial intelligence, the principle of data minimization remains relevant and should not be ignored³¹. Those who develop AI systems must pay careful attention to the type of personal information they use and ensure that the data they use is necessary for their purposes and not merely convenient.

45. The MEQ’s AI system errs on the side of convenience. It uses 1,500 datapoints to generate its prediction³². The dataset contains sensitive information such as the immigration status of students, their medical history (including disabilities), the language they speak at home, the socio-economic index of the school they attend and their home address³³. Not all data points are relevant for the MEQ’s purpose. In fact, the scientific literature shows that relying on a few well-targeted indicators is sufficient to effectively identify students at risk of dropping out:

Cependant, des études longitudinales montrent que bien que les facteurs de risque du

³⁰ *Charte des droits et libertés de la personne*, CQLR, c. C-12, s. 10.

³¹ P-L Déziel, K. Benyekhlef & E. Gaumond, *Repenser la protection des renseignements personnels à la lumière des défis soulevés par l’IA* (OBVIA - Avril 2020) at p. 16.

³² Ministère de l’éducation du Québec, “Solution d’intelligence artificielle pour soutenir la prévention du décrochage scolaire”, (accessed : 29 avril 2026)

³³ Québec, Éducation Québec, *Demande d’accès à des documents administratifs, dossier : 16310/24-757* (accessed 29 avril 2026) at pp. 4-5. (**Exhibit P-2**)

décrochage soient nombreux et d'origines diverses, il n'est pas nécessaire de tous les mesurer pour effectuer un dépistage fiable. La prise en compte de **quelques prédicteurs puissants** du décrochage suffit (soit le rendement, le retard et l'engagement scolaires)³⁴

46. Even the very idea that processing personal information is needed to accurately predict high school dropout can be challenged. Indeed, researchers from Harvard University have studied the data from the Wisconsin dropout prediction system over a period of 8 years (2013-2021). They found that a simple mechanism that only uses information about students' environments—such as their communities, schools, and districts—can target interventions just as efficiently as AI systems that draw upon richer and more individualized sources of data³⁵.
47. This study casts light on the real problem with the MEQ's AI system: it is rooted in the common misconception that processing more data improves accuracy. In fact, small, well-curated datasets are sometimes better suited for some dynamic, multi-causal, and idiosyncratically manifesting phenomena such as high school drop out³⁶.

ii. The AI System does not Comply with the Val-des-Cerfs' Recommendations

48. In *Val-des-Cerfs*, the CAI concluded that two sets of changes were needed for the dropout prediction algorithm to properly safeguard students' data protection rights guaranteed by *Loi sur l'accès*. These recommendations offer a roadmap showing how to improve the AI system to better protect students' privacy. As neither of these changes was implemented, we must conclude that the MEQ's AI system impairs the right to privacy more than what is necessary to achieve the desired objective.
49. The first recommendation the MEQ failed to follow regards its duty to inform the parents about the processing of personal information. In *Val-des-Cerf*, the CAI determined that generating dropout risk factors constitutes a new collection of personal information which triggers s. 65 duty to inform parents of certain elements³⁷:
- a. the name and address of the public body on whose behalf the information is collected;
 - b. the purposes for which the information is collected;
 - c. the categories of persons who will have access to the information;

³⁴ M. Janosz *et al.* "Les élèves du primaire à risque de décrocher au secondaire : caractéristiques à 12 ans et prédicteurs à 7 ans" (Institut de la statistique du Québec : 2013) at p. 3.

³⁵ J. Perdomo *et al.*, "Difficult Lessons on Social Prediction from Wisconsin Public Schools" (2025) *Proceedings of the 2025 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAcT '25)* at pp. 2682, 2689, 2690, 2691.

³⁶ E. B Hekler *et al.*, "Why we need a small data paradigm", (2019) 17:1 *BMC MED* (2019) 133 at p. 3.

³⁷ Art. 65 *Loi sur l'accès* ; Val des cerfs, par. 37,

- d. whether the request is mandatory or optional;
 - e. the consequences for the person concerned or for the third person, as the case may be, for refusing to reply to the request;
 - f. the rights of access and correction provided by law.
 - g. the name of the third persons or categories of third persons to whom it is necessary to release the information for the purposes referred to in subparagraph 2 of the first paragraph, and the possibility that the information could be released outside Québec.
50. While disclosing all these elements is mandatory, the CAI specifically insisted on three items that were particularly important³⁸: (1) the purpose for which the dropout indicator is generated, (2) the categories of persons who will have access to the information and (3) the fact that the law provides parents with the right to access the personal information and correct any inaccuracies³⁹.
51. The email sent by the Centre de services scolaire des Premières-Seigneuries makes no mention of the rights of access and correction and offers only generic answers on the other elements:
- a. **Purpose:** Les renseignements personnels ne serviront qu'à des fins éducatives et d'accompagnement des élèves.
 - b. **Categories of people:** L'accès aux renseignements personnels est strictement limité au personnel pour qui cela est nécessaire dans le cadre de ses fonctions.
52. Such vague statements render the duty to inform under s. 65 meaningless. In *Val-des-Cerfs*, the CAI emphasized that generating the risk indicator is a "significant and distinct"⁴⁰ collection of personal information that requires different information-sharing practices. Schools cannot fulfill their information duty merely by providing the same information that they routinely share with parents⁴¹. They must specifically explain why risk indicators are being generated, and who will be allowed to access them.
53. The algorithm's main purpose is to empower administrators to make data-informed decisions⁴². If the MEQ does not intend to share the risk indicators with teachers working on

³⁸ *Val-des-cerfs*, par 34.

³⁹ *Val-des-cerfs*, par 33

⁴⁰ *Val-des-cerfs*, par 35

⁴¹ *Val-des-cerfs*, par 35

⁴² Québec, Éducation Québec, *Demande d'accès à des documents administratifs, dossier : 16310/24-757* (accessed 29 avril 2026) at p.13 (**Exhibit P-2**) "L'outil vise aussi à répondre aux besoins du réseau, notamment pour soutenir les gestionnaires dans leur prise de décision, tout en gardant l'humain au cœur de ses interventions."

the front lines⁴³, it is unclear what kind of “fins éducatives” the school board refers to in its letter. By providing information so vague as to be misleading, the MEQ and the school boards failed to fulfil the information duty set out in s. 65 of *Loi sur l'accès*.

54. In addition to the elements listed above, the *Loi sur l'accès* (s. 65 al. 2.) also provides that the MEQ must inform parents about the involvement of third parties, if there are any, and discuss the possibility of personal information being shared outside of Quebec, if applicable.
55. Neither the letters sent to parents⁴⁴ nor the information leaflet⁴⁵ associated with the project mentions the involvement of any third parties. Based on these documents, one would reasonably believe that the project is a joint initiative of the MEQ and the school boards.
26. This is only partly true. In fact, the project is managed by the Société de gestion des réseaux informatiques des commissions scolaires (GRICS), which collaborated with a start-up to develop the solution⁴⁶. GRICS is a private entity that describes itself as “la plus importante entreprise de technologie de l’information spécialisée en éducation au Québec.”⁴⁷ It performs most of the work on the project—including processing the data and training the algorithm. Because GRICS is a private entity with a financial interest in keeping the technical aspects of its system confidential, the MEQ claims it cannot disclose the algorithm’s technical details⁴⁸. As a result, the functioning of the algorithm escapes public scrutiny.
56. This lack of transparency is a violation of the second alinea of s. 65 of *Loi sur l'accès*. Failing to share information about GRICS’s involvement is consequential because it makes it

⁴³ Québec, Éducation Québec, *Demande d'accès à des documents administratifs, dossier : 16310/24-757* (accessed 29 avril 2026) at p. 13. (**Exhibit P-2**) “dans une première phase, la solution s’adresse aux directions générales des CSS/CS. Éventuellement, elle s’adressera aussi aux directeurs d’établissement”

⁴⁴ **Exhibit P-4**

⁴⁵ Québec, Ministère de l’éducation du Québec, “Feuillet_Solution_IA_Decrochage_scolaire_VF.pdf (**Exhibit P-9**)

⁴⁶ Société de gestion des réseaux informatiques des commissions scolaires, *La GRICS, lauréate au concours des OCTAS!* <https://grics.ca/la-grics-laureate-au-concours-des-octas/> (en ligne). (accessed 29 avril 2026). (**Exhibit P-10**) “Ce module, offert en partenariat avec la firme Optania depuis 2017, a permis à la GRICS d’accélérer la mise en place de l’intelligence artificielle dans son outil Mozaïk-Portail. La Veille active permet aux enseignants et aux directions de déceler plus facilement les difficultés de leurs élèves, d’intervenir rapidement et ainsi, de lutter contre le décrochage en analysant les profils scolaires en temps réel, de façon entièrement automatisée.”

⁴⁷ Société de gestion des réseaux informatiques des commissions scolaires, *Nous pouvons vous aider*, <https://grics.ca/grics/> (en ligne). (accessed 29 avril 2026). (**Exhibit P-10**)

⁴⁸ Québec, Éducation Québec, *Demande d'accès à des documents administratifs, dossier : 16310/24-757* (accessed 29 avril 2026) at p. 1. (**Exhibit P-2**) “Toutefois, l’un des documents visés par votre demande est formé en substance de renseignements techniques fourni par un tiers, la société GRICS. Ainsi, ce document ne peut pas vous être transmis suivant les articles 14, 23 et 24 de la Loi sur l’accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels (RLRQ, chapitre A-2.1, ci-après « la Loi »).”

harder for parents to identify who processes the data, and where the data processing takes place. Such opacity about the involvement of third parties could undermine parents' trust in the government's handling of personal information.

57. Finally, the MEQ failed to meaningfully implement the CAI's recommendation with respect to the deletion of personal information. In *Val-des-Cerfs*, the CAI recommended revising the policy regarding the disposal of the new personal information generated by the algorithm. It suggested destroying the information once students are no longer under the school's authority—that is, once the school can no longer intervene with them⁴⁹.
58. It is unclear whether the MEQ revised its data deletion policy to comply with the CAI's recommendation as the MEQ refuses to share the technical information managed by the intermediary responsible for deploying the solution (GRICS)⁵⁰. That said, the broad and vague purpose the MEQ chose for its collection of personal information opens the door to retaining students' personal information longer than the CAI recommends. Under s. 73 of *Loi sur l'accès*, personal information must be destroyed or anonymized once the purpose for which it was collected has been achieved. In other words, this means that nothing currently prevents using the risk factors after a student has left the education system.
59. Given that the MEQ's AI system runs contrary to the principle of data minimization, and that it does not comply with the recommendations the CAI made in *Val-des-Cerfs*, the MEQ's algorithm fails on the third step of the necessity test. In its current state, the dropout prediction algorithm does not constitute the least invasive way to optimize interventions with students in order to maximize their chances of educational success.

c) The Privacy Implications Outweigh the Benefits of the AI System

60. The last step of the proportionality analysis is determining whether the benefits of the AI system outweigh its negative impacts. They do not. The datafication of students' lives contributes to creating a stressful environment that causes distress among students and hinders their ability to develop autonomy and become independent thinkers. Even if there were a marginal improvement in the MEQ's ability to identify students who are unlikely to finish high school, it is not sufficient to justify these negative consequences. Thus the MEQ's AI system fails on the final step of the proportionality analysis.
61. To fully appreciate this last argument, it is worth remembering the purpose of data protection

⁴⁹ *Val-des-Cerfs*, par 44.

⁵⁰ Québec, Éducation Québec, *Demande d'accès à des documents administratifs, dossier : 16310/24-757* (accessed 29 avril 2026) at p. 1. (**Exhibit P-2**) "Toutefois, l'un des documents visés par votre demande est formé en substance de renseignements techniques fourni par un tiers, la société GRICS. Ainsi, ce document ne peut pas vous être transmis suivant les articles 14, 23 et 24 de la Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels (RLRQ, chapitre A-2.1, ci-après « la Loi »)."

rights. Modern data protection laws such as *Loi sur l'accès* are heavily influenced by the ideas of the American law professor Alan Westin. In his seminal work *Privacy and Freedom*, which laid the foundation for modern privacy law, Westin affirms that privacy is vital to the development of autonomy and individuality which are core tenets of democratic societies.

62. According to Westin, the “development of individuality is particularly important in democratic societies, since [in these societies] qualities of independent thought, diversity of views, and non-conformity are considered desirable traits for individuals.”⁵¹ He then adds that gaining “[s]uch independence requires time for sheltered experimentation and testing of ideas, for preparation and practice in thought and conduct, without fear of ridicule or penalty.”⁵²
63. Schools are one of the places where the free experimentation described by Westin takes place. This is why data protection laws such as *Loi sur l'accès* should provide robust safeguards to protect the privacy of students who are evolving in those environments. The implementation of an algorithm that monitors virtually all aspects of their lives—including their grades, their native language, their relationship with their parents and their health records⁵³—hinders students’ ability to freely explore and discover who they are. Unrestricted datafication of students’ academic life undermines the idea of the school as a sheltered place that welcomes exploration.
64. In a paper entitled : *AI in education: learner choice and fundamental rights*, three law and education scholars argue that “Educational institutions are not simply locations where teaching takes place, but also serve as protected spaces where learners are (in theory) free from social, political and economic pressures. The continuous assessment of student performance, as opposed to being tested at milestone intervals, places learners under continuous stress⁵⁴”.
65. Being continually monitored discourages exploration. In fact, it fosters anticipatory conformity—a term that describes students’ propensity to adjust their behaviour to conform to the norm and avoid being classified negatively by the algorithm⁵⁵. In *Chilling Effects, Repression, Conformity and Power in the Digital Age*, Canadian law professor Jonathon

⁵¹ Alan Westin, *Privacy and Freedom*, (Atheneum, 1967) at pp. 33-34.

⁵² Alan Westin, *Privacy and Freedom*, (Atheneum, 1967) at pp. 33-34.

⁵³ Québec, Éducation Québec, *Demande d'accès à des documents administratifs, dossier : 16310/24-757* (accessed 29 april 2026) at pp. 4-5. (**Exhibit P-2**)

⁵⁴ B. Berendt, A. Littlejohn & M. Blakemore, “AI in education: learner choice and fundamental rights” (2020) 45:3 *Learning, Media and Technology* at p. 7.

⁵⁵ K. McConvey & S. Guha, “‘This is not a data problem’: Algorithms and Power in Public Higher Education in Canada” (2024) *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing System* at p. 10, 12.

Penney explains how the systematic observation of people through data collection and analysis encourages compliance and conformity to the norm⁵⁶. He also explains how surveillance, even when seemingly benign or benevolent tend to cause anxiety, anger, distress, and nervousness⁵⁷.

66. The negative impacts of the dropout prediction algorithm are substantial and outweigh its potential benefits, which are limited, at best. As we have shown, the MEQ's algorithm is likely biased and risks causing discrimination as well as hindering students' ability to develop their autonomy and individuality. On the other hand, the benefits of the algorithm are hard to pinpoint. The objective of the AI system is not clearly defined, nor is the way it will be used, and the relevance of using an algorithm to prevent dropout more effectively altogether remains to be proven.
67. The right to privacy and data protection are constitutional and quasi-constitutional rights. Consequently, any infringement of these rights must meet a high threshold under the necessity test. The MEQ's algorithm does not meet this standard. This is why we respectfully request that the MEQ pause the use of its AI system until it meaningfully complies with *Loi sur l'accès* and the CAI's recommendations in *Val-des-Cerfs*.

⁵⁶ J. Penney, *Chilling Effects, Repression, Conformity and Power in the Digital Age*, (Cambridge University Press, 2025) at pp. 51-54.

⁵⁷ J. Penney, *Chilling Effects, Repression, Conformity and Power in the Digital Age*, (Cambridge University Press, 2025) at pp. 51-54.

68. FOR THESE REASONS, THE APPLICANT RESPECTFULLY REQUESTS THAT THE CAI:

IMPOSE a moratorium on the use of drop out prediction algorithms until a privacy impact assessment has been conducted completed in accordance with section 64 of the *Loi sur l'accès*, and made publicly available.

ORDER that the AI model and all the data it generated before the publication of the privacy impact assessment be deleted.

ORDER that the MEQ meaningfully complies with *Loi sur l'accès* and the CAI's recommendations in *Val-des-Cerfs* before deploying another dropout prediction AI system.

Québec, May 21, 2026

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Exhibits supporting the application

EXHIBIT P-1: Article from Le Devoir titled "L'IA est mise au service de la lutte contre le décrochage scolaire. Mais à quel prix?" (January 14, 2026)

EXHIBIT P-2: Documents obtained through an access to information request about the "Solution d'intelligence artificielle pour soutenir la prévention du décrochage scolaire" (April 15, 2025)

EXHIBIT P-3: Article from La Tribune titled "Un outil antidécrochage sera utilisé dans toutes les écoles du Québec" (January 30, 2025)

EXHIBIT P-4: Email exchanges between the Plaintiff and the Respondents (en liasse)

EXHIBIT P-5: Complaint to the Protecteur du citoyen (April 4, 2025)

EXHIBIT P-6: Response to an access to information request denying access to the PIA (April 14, 2025)

EXHIBIT P-7: Response from the Protecteur du citoyen informing the Plaintiff that he does not have jurisdiction over her complaint (May 15, 2025)

EXHIBIT P-8: Notice that the Protecteur du citoyen transferred the Plaintiff's complaint to the CAI (May 26, 2025)

EXHIBIT P-9: Copy of the information leaflet created by the MEQ to inform parents about the dropout prediction algorithm (Last modified on September 27, 2024)

EXHIBIT P-10: Screenshots regarding the involvement of a third party (GRICS) in the development of the MEQ's AI system (taken on May 12, 2026)

PART IV - TABLE OF AUTHORITIES

Statutes and Regulations	Tab	Web
<i>Loi sur l'accès aux documents des organismes publics et sur la protection des renseignements personnels</i> CQLR c. A-2.1.	N/A	Web
<i>Loi modernisant des dispositions législatives en matière de protection des renseignements personnels</i> , SQ 2021, c 25	N/A	Web
<i>Énoncé de principe pour une utilisation responsable de l'intelligence artificielle par les organismes public</i> AM 2024-02 (QC)	N/A	Web
<i>Charte des droits et libertés de la personne</i> , CQLR, c. C-12.	N/A	Web

Cases	Tab	Web
<i>Centre de services scolaire du- Val- des- Cerfs (anciennement Commission scolaire du Val-des-Cerfs)</i> CAI 1020040-S	N/A	Web
<i>Laval (Ville) c. X.</i> , 2003 CanLII 44085 (QC CQ)	N/A	Web
<i>RJR-MacDonald Inc. v. Canada (Attorney General)</i> , 1995 CanLII 64 (SCC)	N/A	Web
<i>Carter c. Canada (Procureur général)</i> , 2015 CSC 5	N/A	Web

Doctrine	Tab	Web
Ministère de l'Éducation du Québec, "Recommandations éthiques de l'intelligence artificielle en éducation" (2026).	N/A	Web
S. Collin et al "Enjeux éthiques et critiques de l'intelligence artificielle en éducation : une revue systématique de la littérature" (2023) 49-4 <i>Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology</i> 1	1	N/A
L. Weinberg, <i>Smart University - Student Surveillance in the Digital Age</i> , (John Hopkins University Press, 2024) at p. 72.	2	N/A
P-L Déziel, K. Benyekhlef & E. Gaumont, <i>Repenser la protection des renseignements personnels à la lumière des défis soulevés par l'IA</i> (OBVIA - Avril 2020) at p. 16.	N/A	Web

M. Janosz <i>et al.</i> “Les élèves du primaire à risque de décrocher au secondaire : caractéristiques à 12 ans et prédicteurs à 7 ans” (Institut de la statistiques du Québec : 2013)	N/A	Web
J. Perdomo <i>et al.</i> , “Difficult Lessons on Social Prediction from Wisconsin Public Schools” (2025) <i>Proceedings of the 2025 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '25)</i>	3	N/A
E. B Hekler <i>et al.</i> , “Why we need a small data paradigm”, (2019) 17:1 <i>BMC MED</i> (2019) 133	4	N/A
A. Westin, <i>Privacy and Freedom</i> , (Atheneum, 1967)	5	Web
B. Berendt, A. Littlejohn & M. Blakemore, “AI in education: learner choice and fundamental rights” (2020) 45:3 <i>Learning, Media and Technology</i>	6	N/A
K. McConvey & S. Guha, ““This is not a data problem’: Algorithms and Power in Public Higher Education in Canada” (2024) <i>Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing System</i>	7	N/A
J. Penney, <i>Chilling Effects, Repression, Conformity and Power in the Digital Age</i> , (Cambridge University Press, 2025)	8	N/A